

Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice of Unused and Expired Drugs Disposal among Medical Students of ACSR Government Medical CollegeSushma Chinnakandukuru¹, Thutakula Kavitha², M.Anitha³, M.R. Kiran Kumar⁴¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacology, ACSR Government Medical College, Nellore²Assistant professor, Department of Anatomy, ACSR Government Medical College, Nellore³Assistant professor, Department of transfusion medicine, ACSR Government Medical College, Nellore⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Emergency Medicine, ACSR Government Medical College, Nellore

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Abstract:**Introduction:** The accumulation of unused and expired medicines at home creates environmental dangers due to a lack of information about proper pharmaceutical disposal practices.**Aim:** The current study is to assess students' knowledge, attitudes, and disposal processes for unused or expired medicines, as well as to create an awareness session.**Materials and Methods:** This cross-sectional, questionnaire-based investigation was undertaken with undergraduate medical students. The questionnaire contains demographic information about the students, questions about their knowledge of safe disposal of expired/unused pharmaceuticals, questions about their attitudes towards safe disposal of expired/unused drugs, and questions about their practices regarding safe disposal of expired/unused drugs.**Results:** A total of 100 medical undergraduate students participated, with 53% female and 47% male. 83% of pupils indicated that they are aware of pharmaceutical waste. Sixty-one percent of pupils knew how to dispose of narcotics safely. The majority of students (93%) agreed that hazardous disposal of expired or unused pharmaceuticals would harm both the environment and human health. 58% of students strongly agreed that the public and students should be educated about the adverse impacts of improper methods of disposing of unused, expired, and leftover pharmaceuticals on human and environmental health. When the survey participants were asked if they store unneeded or leftover medications at home, 66% replied yes, while 44% said no. According to study participants' responses, topical formulations (60%) were the most prevalent type of drug stored in houses, followed by antipyretics (17%), antibiotics (13%), antacids (4%), analgesics (4%), and antihistamines (2%). When asked about how they dispose of leftover medications, the majority of students (73%) said they toss them in dust bins at home, which would be collected by the municipality. Few participants (7%) stated that they would return to the chemist and rinse down into the sink for safe disposal, whereas 6% and 3% of students preferred to flush down the toilet and give away to friends and family. Self-discontinuation is the most common cause for drug storage among participants (39%). Other survey participants reported that they had gathered the drugs because they had purchased them over the counter for common colds and headaches (16%), and that many of the drugs had expired (25%).**Conclusion:** In the current study, medical undergraduate students were aware of the risks associated with inappropriate disposal of expired or unused medications. Whereas, due to a lack of understanding about safer procedures, the majority of students used unsuitable techniques to dispose of leftover or expired medication at home.**Keywords:** Expired medication; Medication Disposal; Medical Students; Knowledge.

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Introduction

The global use of prescription and over-the-counter medications is increasing, with over 4.5 trillion doses projected in 2020, a 24% increase from 2015 [1]. However, the patient may not use all of the prescription medications, and substantial volumes may remain unused or expired [2]. Medication accumulation in households can occur for a variety of reasons, including drug side effects, changes in

dosage/regimen, recovery from illness, medicine expiration, promotional influence by manufacturers, physician prescribing practices, dispensing practices, and patient nonadherence [2-5]. Patients may also retain medications at home in case they need them later [6, 7]. The buildup of unwanted, unused, or expired medicines at home might pose an environmental risk due to a lack of awareness

about proper medicine disposal practices [8]. Unused and expired drugs might enter the environment when they are discarded in domestic garbage or liquid pharmaceuticals are disposed of in the sewage system.

The introduction of these drugs into the ecosystem can pose a variety of environmental risks. Accidental drug poisoning and misuse are serious consequences of improper medication disposal, especially among young children and teenagers.

The current study aims to assess students' knowledge, attitudes, and disposal methods for unused or expired pharmaceuticals, as well as to create an awareness session.

Material & Methods

This study was carried out among the undergraduate medical students of all the professional years of ACSR Government Medical College, Nellore after obtaining Scientific committee & IEC approval from the Institute.

Study Design: Descriptive cross-sectional Study.

Study Area: Department of Pharmacology, ACSR government medical college, Nellore.

Sample size: All Voluntary Participants (n=100).

Pre-Test Questionnaire was given to the students in the form of Google forms who were included in the study. Followed by an awareness programme on the safe disposal of drugs and a post test was conducted with the same questionnaire in Google forms.

Inclusion Criteria: All Professional year students of ACSR Government Medical College were included based on the interest to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Those who are not willing to participate.

Data Collection: Students provided the data with pretested prestructured questionnaire which consists knowledge, attitudes, and disposal procedures for unused or expired drugs. Data was entered in an Excel sheet and mentioned as percentage frequency.

Results

Table 1: Attitude of students toward the unsafe disposal of expired & unused medications

Questions related to attitude of the students	Strongly agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Strongly disagree (%)	Disagree (%)
There is an inadequate information regarding scientific disposal of expired, unused and left-over medications	27	66	6	0	1.0
The risks associated with unscientific and improper disposal of expired, unused and leftover medications is more in children.	40	55	6	0	2.0
Healthcare professionals such as doctors, pharmacists, and nurses must provide information on proper expired, unused, and left-over medications.	59	39	2	0	0
Educational activities such as drug take-back programs related to expired, unused, and left-over medications should be conducted	50	43	4	0	3.0
It is important to conduct Educational Programs on the harms associated with inappropriate disposal practices and safer disposal methods of unused or expired medications among the common population.	58	37	4	0	0

Table 2: Number of unused/leftover drugs at home of study participants

Number of drugs	Number of students	Percentage
0	15	15.0
1-5	61	61.0
6-10	10	10.0
11-25	5	5.0
>25	9	9.0

Table 3: Classes of unused/expired drugs stored at home

Number of drugs	Number of students	Percentage
Anti-histamines	2	2.0
Analgesics	4	4.0

Antacids	4	4.0
Antibiotics	13	13.0
Antipyretics	18	18.0
Topical formulations	63	63.0

Table 4: Methods used for disposal of unused/expired medications

Number of drugs	Number of students	Percentage
Rising down a sink	7	7
Flushing down in toilet	6	6
Return to Pharmacist	7	7
Municipality collection at home	73	73
Giving away to relatives, friends etc	3	3
Others	4	4

Table 5: Reasons for possession of unused/expired medications

Number of drugs	Number of students (n)	Percentage
Doctor changed treatment	5	5.0
Prescribed more than needed	5	5.0
Self-discontinuation after condition resolved	39	39.0
Leftover from previous over the counter drug purchase	16	16.0
Passed expiry date	25	25.0
Adverse effect to prescribed drugs	3	3.0
Other	7	7.0

Discussion

Medications are used not only to cure diseases, but also to diagnose and prevent them. Patients do not use all of the prescribed pharmaceuticals; as a result of poor adherence to therapy, there is a risk of stockpiling unused or expired medications at home. It is critical to establish practical and scientific rules for safely disposing of expired, unused, and leftover pharmaceuticals. Most developing countries lack standardised procedures for properly disposing of expired, unused, and leftover pharmaceuticals. There have been very few studies in this region to assess knowledge about safe disposal of unwanted pharmaceuticals.

As a result, the current study was done to analyse the knowledge, attitude, and practice of disposing of unused or expired pharmaceuticals among medical students at our college. The questionnaire has three parts: Part I contains participant demographic information as well as questions about the safe disposal of expired, unused, and leftover medications; Part II contains questions about attitudes towards the safe disposal of expired, unused, and leftover medications; and Part III contains questions about practices for the safe disposal of expired, unused, and leftover medications. Prior to starting the study, topic experts evaluated the questionnaire. The study was conducted online.

All participants were provided Google forms with questions, and their responses were analysed. The study included a total of 100 medical graduate students. Of the 100 students, 53% were female and 47% were male. 83% of students stated that they are aware of medical waste, whereas 17% were

unaware of it. 61% of students were aware of the proper disposal of expired, unused, and leftover pharmaceuticals, while 39% were unaware of what to do with expired or unused prescriptions. This awareness among the current study participants was considerably better when compared to the study done by Kachhap et al., where only 35% of the study participants were aware of the negative effect of unsafe disposal of pharmaceutical waste [9].

The majority of students (93%) agreed that hazardous disposal of expired or unused pharmaceuticals would harm both the environment and human health. solely 5% of interviewees said it solely affects environmental health and isn't damaging to animal or human health. Approximately 59% of students believe that chemists are the best people to advise them through the proper disposal of expired, unused, and leftover pharmaceuticals. Few study participants felt that doctors (21%), nurses (13%), and the media (6%), can all provide information about safe medication disposal.

In a survey conducted by Kampamba et al., the majority of participants stated that the most appropriate way to teach people about the safe disposal of expired, unused, and leftover pharmaceuticals was through mass media (51.9%), chemists (26%), doctors (16.9%), and nurses (5.0%) [10].

According to the responses of a few students, alternative options include limiting the amount of prescriptions prescribed by the doctor (5%) and donating unneeded drugs (3%). In the current survey, the majority of students were positive about the safe disposal of expired, unused, and leftover pharma-

ceuticals. 58% of the students strongly agreed that the public and students should be taught about the negative impacts of improper methods of disposing of unwanted, expired, and leftover pharmaceuticals on both humans and the environment.

And 58% of students strongly agreed that educational initiatives such as take-back programs should be offered to the general public.

When the survey participants were asked if they store unneeded or leftover medications at home, 66% replied yes, while 44% said no.

About 15% of students stated they don't have any leftover meds at home right now, while 61% claimed they have unused drugs ranging from one to five at home. Only 9% of students stated that they might have more than 25 unused medications at home.

According to the responses of the current survey participants, topical formulations (60%) were the most prevalent type of drug stored in households, followed by antipyretics (17%), antibiotics (13%), antacids (4%), analgesics (4%), and antihistamines (2%).

These findings differed from those of Jindal and Goel, who found that analgesics (34%) were the most commonly stored drug group, followed by antibiotics (29%) and antipyretics (11%) [11].

These disparities could be attributed to variances in disease prevalence and regional prescribing trends.

When asked about how they dispose of leftover medications, the majority of students (73%) said they toss them in dust bins at home, which are collected by the municipality. Few participants (7%) stated that they would return to the chemist and rinse down into the sink for safe disposal, whereas 6% and 3% of students preferred to flush down the toilet and give away to friends and family.

According to a survey, the most prevalent cause for storing unneeded medicines at home was self-discontinuation of prescribed drugs once patients felt better from the disease and purchasing over-the-counter drugs (48.1%) [12].

Self-discontinuation was the most common cause for drug storage among the study subjects (39%). This is most likely related to an improvement in illness symptoms or pharmacological side effects such as gastritis and nausea. Other survey participants reported that they had gathered the drugs because they had purchased them over the counter for common colds and headaches (16%), and that many of the drugs had expired (25%).

The most generally mentioned reasons for having leftover medicines were an improvement in medical condition, a change in medicines prescribed by a doctor, keeping for future use, and an unaccepta-

ble medicine side effect. This was consistent with earlier studies, which found that reasons for retaining unneeded drugs in the home include improving medical condition, storing for future use, changing regimens, and drug side effects [2, 12].

The conclusion is consistent with research undertaken in Ethiopia [13, 14] and elsewhere in the world [4, 6, 15, 16, 17]. In another survey, nearly two-thirds of respondents reported burning leftover medicines as an alternative method of disposing of both unused and expired household medicines [18]. Only a few participants reported returning unused or expired medications to healthcare facilities/providers. This is consistent with a prior study from Ethiopia [13]. The explanation could be a lack of information about how to properly dispose of unused/expired medications. However, other studies from Europe and abroad found a higher level of unused and expired medicine that had been returned to pharmacies or healthcare facilities [19, 20]. The low incidence of unused and expired pharmaceutical returns seen in our study could be attributed to a lack of an established medication take-back program. More than 80% of participants disposed or agreed to discard unwanted and expired medications in their original packaging.

This result was consistent with earlier investigations [19, 20]. This approach was not in accordance with the established methods of dumping expired and unused drugs, and it could lead to unintentional poisoning and abuse if the disposed medicines were habit-forming [21].

Other plausible causes for retaining unused pharmaceuticals included a physician changing the regimen, prescribing more drugs than necessary and adverse drug effects in 5%, 5%, and 3% of total individuals.

The practice of discarding unused/expired pharmaceutical trash contradicts national pharmaceutical waste management instructions.

Conclusion

The majority of survey participants disposed of expired or unused medications in domestic garbage and toilet/sink. To safeguard the public and the ecology, it is critical to raise awareness about the proper manner of disposing of medical waste and the consequences of improper disposal practices through an appropriate medium of communication.

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